

YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF STARTUP CULTURE

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Annotation: This thesis study examines the problem of youth employment in Uzbekistan and the role of startup culture in solving it. The work analyzes the main causes of youth unemployment, problems in the current labor market, and opportunities for creating new jobs through innovative entrepreneurship. It also provides information on the formation of the startup ecosystem in Uzbekistan, existing programs, and their effectiveness. At the end of the work, proposals and recommendations were developed for the development of startup culture to increase youth employment. The thesis is written on the basis of scientific and theoretical approaches and practical examples, and is relevant in the framework of youth policy and economic reforms.

Keywords: youth employment, startup culture, unemployment, innovative entrepreneurship, labor market, Uzbekistan, youth policy, startup ecosystem, economic development, digital economy.

In today's globalization environment, innovative approaches play an important role in all sectors of the economy. In particular, increasing the economic activity of young people, successfully attracting them to the labor market and ensuring their employment are among the priorities of state policy. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to fully utilizing the potential of young people, forming them as enterprising, innovative-thinking personnel with modern knowledge and skills.

At the same time, the development of a startup culture is becoming increasingly important in ensuring youth employment. Because startups are not only business projects based on new ideas, but also a means of creating new jobs for young people and forming an innovative environment in the economy. In recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale measures to support the startup environment through IT Parks, technoparks, grants and incubation programs.

The purpose of this thesis is to analyze youth employment problems and study the role and importance of startup culture in solving them. Ushbu maqsadga erishish uchun quyidagi vazifalar belgilangan:

- to highlight the theoretical foundations of youth employment;
- to analyze the formation and development of startup culture;
- to study the current state of youth employment in Uzbekistan;
- to assess the opportunities for creating jobs for young people through startups;
- to develop problems and proposals

The object of the study is the processes of youth employment in Uzbekistan, and the subject is the role and influence of startup culture in these processes. The work uses comparative analysis, statistical methods, a logical approach, and systematic analysis methods.

Youth employment is the opportunity for the able-bodied young generation to have a permanent job, participate in economic activity, and earn an income. Employment is one of the factors that ensures not only economic stability, but also social harmony in society. In particular, youth is considered the most active, growth-oriented, and potential period in a person's life. Therefore, the effective involvement of this category in the labor market is of strategic importance for the development of the country.

According to the UN and the International Labor Organization, young people make up a significant portion of the world's unemployed. Uzbekistan is also implementing large-scale reforms to increase youth employment and actively involve them in economic life. The concept of a startup and its main characteristics:

A startup is a business initiative that aims to grow rapidly based on innovation, technology, or an innovative approach, unlike traditional businesses. Startups are often created by small teams and are associated with a high level of uncertainty and risk. However, they also have high returns and broad development opportunities.

Startup culture is a socio-economic environment that encourages innovative thinking, creativity, independent work, and the creation of competitive products. This culture is closely related to technological progress, modern knowledge, and the needs of the global market.

Youth and startups: theoretical approaches. Young people are open to innovation, quickly adopt technologies, and are willing to take risks, and they play a huge role in promoting startup initiatives. The experience of developed countries shows that startups created by young people not only provide employment, but also bring new directions to the economy. According to the theory of innovative economics, creating innovations allows for more efficient use of resources. Also, according to Schumpeter's theory of entrepreneurship, startups provide an impetus for renewal in the existing economic system through "creative destruction". This requires the active participation of young people.

Youth employment situation in Uzbekistan: statistical analysis.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of 2024, young people will make up about 60 percent of the population. This indicates that the main part of the labor resources is made up of the young generation. According to the State Statistics Committee, the unemployment rate among citizens aged 16–30 is around 8–10%, which is a serious challenge for the country's development. Several factors contribute to low youth employment:

- increased competition in the labor market;
- mismatch between professional skills and market demand;
- insufficient access to financial and information resources;
- regional inequality (more job opportunities in cities, fewer in rural areas).

There is a growing need for modern and innovative approaches to address this situation. One such solution is to develop a startup culture among young people.

Startups and youth: practical examples from Uzbekistan. In recent years, great attention has been paid to the development of startups in Uzbekistan. In particular:

More than 800 startups were registered as part of the IT Park project in 2023; Thousands of young entrepreneurs have been provided with preferential loans and grants through the state program "Youth is our future"; Startup Academies and technoparks in the regions are becoming centers of knowledge and practical skills for young people. For example, the Sunar Solar Tech startup, created by young people in the Namangan region, produces compact power sources based on solar energy. This is not only environmentally beneficial, but also serves to create dozens of jobs. Such examples exist in every region, through which young people are putting their ideas into practice and joining the economy.

There are several challenges in the formation of a startup environment:

-limited funding sources;

-lack of experience and knowledge;

-weak mechanisms for contacting investors;

-fear of making mistakes, i.e. cultural fear.

-at the same time, the existing opportunities are worth noting:

-government grants, soft loans and tax breaks;

-startup competitions and accelerator programs supported by international organizations; the widespread use of digital technologies.

A number of practical proposals have been developed to develop youth employment and a startup culture in Uzbekistan:

1. Strengthening entrepreneurship promotion: It is necessary to encourage young people to create startups, expand preferential credit and grant programs to provide them with initial capital. It is also important to establish cooperation with private investors and international organizations for innovative projects. Young entrepreneurs should be provided with consulting and mentoring services, helping them in their business development.

2. Improving experience exchange and educational programs: Create special educational programs for young people on the development of innovative ideas and startups. It is also necessary to organize training courses and seminars in the fields of high technology and the digital economy. This will not only keep young people busy, but also give them the opportunity to understand the global market.

3. Creating preferential conditions for startups: It is necessary to create free zones for startups, reduce tax rates for them, and provide them with technological infrastructure and digital resources. It is also necessary to introduce a system of short-term preferential loans for startups by state organizations and banks.

Conclusions

This thesis analyzes important issues related to youth employment and the development of startup culture. Despite the high effectiveness of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan on youth employment and the development of startups, there are still many problems in this regard. More effective measures should be taken to increase the activity of young people in the labor market, expand innovative approaches, and develop startup culture.

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